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Industrial monuments - gains and losses

Athanasios Chatsigogas,
P.I.O.P. (Cultural Foundation of Pireaus Bank)
exatz@tee.gr

In recent years, industrial monuments in Greece have been taking a place of their own, maybe not the one we would wish for, but still a clearly recognisable place, among the monuments of culture.

In many cities of Greece, important high-quality projects have been completed in the last 15 years:

The Technological-Cultural Park at **Lavrio** in the metallurgy complex of the French Company, the Industrial Museum on the island of **Syros**, the olive-presses and soapworks of **Lesvos** island as cultural sites, the restored Tsalapatas Brick and Tile Factory at **Volos**, the Waterpower Museum in the watermills of **Dimititsana**, the Museum of the Olive at **Sparta**, and the Water Museum in the old waterpump-station of **Thessaloniki** are the most serious projects for the highlighting of monuments of technical culture.

Projects no less important have been carried out by the revival of a number of industrial monuments along the old industrial axis connecting **Piraeus** with **Athens**. These are the 'Technopolis' in the Gasworks and the "Melina Mercouri" Cultural Centre in the *Poulopoulos Hat Factory*, projects that were undertaken by the Municipality of Athens, the new School of Fine Arts in the *Sikiaridis Textile Factory* and the recent creation of two Athens Festival theatre premises in the *Tsaousoglou Furniture Factories* and the "Sanitas"

"Paperworks. Also particularly encouraging is the prospect of the installation of the library of Parliament in the Public Tobacco Factory of Athens.

The Municipality of **Volos** has continued its utilisation of the city's historic industrial assets by the operation of the City Museum in what was the *Papantou Tobacco Warehouse*. This project is expected to be completed in 2008.

At **Karditsa**, on the initiative of the Municipality, the old water supply pumping-station has been converted into a museum. In **Thessaly**, a number of minor projects which involve the conversion of old industrial premises into exhibition halls and cultural venues are in progress (e.g., the *Hatziyannis olive press* in the Municipality of **Portaria**, the *Fappas flour-mill* in the Municipality of **Sipiada**, etc.).

In **Macedonia**, the Technology Management Department of the University of Macedonia has been established in the restored *Longos - Kyrtsis - Tourpalis Textile Factory* at **Naousa**. At **Veria**, the *Markos Mill* has been restored in order to house the city's Byzantine Museum, while at **Edessa** the restoration of the watermills continues.

During the past few years many positive steps have been taken in the field of railways to highlight the old nineteenth-century and early twentieth-century network. Good examples are the declaration as a monument in operation of the mountain narrow gauge rack-and-pinion railway alongside the **Vouraikos** river in **Peloponnese**, the declaration of large sections of the railways and of the stations throughout Greece as monuments, the working restoration of the narrow gauge steam railway on **Mt Pelion**, in **Thessaly**, and the restoration of the railway stations in **Piraeus**, **Theseion**, **Monastiraki**, **Omonia** and **Victoria** for the capital's first electric-powered metro line.

All these projects have been based on, and have been completed thanks to a status of protection which took shape with the declaration of monuments, mainly in the 1990s. Unfortunately, during the preparation for the Athens Olympic Games of 2004, this positive climate was reversed. The "explosion" in the real estate market and the "priority" given to the organisation of the Games led the Ministry of Culture to a change of policy. This attitude has been persisting up to the present. During the last three years there have been lots of cases, in which industrial monuments have been frequently assessed for their uses not on the criteria of science but on exclusively market considerations. Their fate has been determined by the intention of the owners to escape from a burden and by the refusal of the state to support the cost of restoration with funding.

The result of this new attitude and practice has been the partial or complete destruction of important historic industrial units throughout Greece :

In **Piraeus**, the *Chemical Products and Fertilisers Factory* was demolished in 2003, the *Retsinas Textile Works* was destroyed at the same period by fire after it had been scheduled for preservation, and the *Saportas Tobacco Factory* was demolished in 2005. The *Cereals Silo* on **Kavala** harbour were also demolished in 2005. In **Thessaloniki**, the *Fix Brewery* is endangered by partial declassification. The *Hatziyannakis - Altinalmazis Flourmill* was also destroyed by fire in 2005, without having been the subject of a preservation order. In **Athens**, the greater part of the *Columbia Music Records Factory* was taken down in 2006, as well as the *Anatoliki Carpet Factory*, while a series of historic industrial monuments such as the *Lime Kiln* in **Galatsi** and the *Cardboard Packing Factory* in **Kolonos** are directly being in danger.

It is worth noting that at this same period, 2003 - 2006, thanks to the initiatives of groups of citizens, academic institutions and, occasionally, the municipal authorities, the destruction of other monuments, such as the *Kronos Alcohol Factory* and the *Iris Paintworks* at **Elefsina**, the *Votrys* and *Kambas Wineries* in **Athens**, and the *Matsangos Tobacco Factory* in **Volos**, has been averted.

Research and education

Research into industrial archaeology is nowadays carried out in a number of university departments in Greece, mostly of architecture and history.

In the Architecture Faculty of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), the "Historic Mines of the Aegean" research program has made a record of all the establishments of the nineteenth and twentieth century in the islands.

Two major historic industrial complexes, those of the *Chemical Fertilisers Company* at **Drapetsona (Piraeus)** and of the *Public Power Corporation* at **Ptolemaida in Macedonia**, have also been studied. There have been suggested re-use solutions for both of them. The first one was demolished, immediately after the completion of the research project, while for the second one the study suggested the setting up of an "Energy - Technology Park".

Within the framework of the postgraduate program on the protection of monuments of the NTUA a course on industrial archaeology has been included, and in recent years, scores of degree theses on Greek industrial monuments have been compiled.

At the *Thessaloniki Polytechnic*, a special postgraduate workshop was devoted for two years to the study of the *Fix Brewery* complex. At the same university, the Civil Engineering Department is elaborating models for the restoration of lighthouses within an international program.

Within the framework of the European inter-state action on "The industrial heritage between land and sea", which is directed by the Ministry of Culture, a workshop on the "Eco-Museum of the **Pagasetic Gulf**" took place in the Department of Architecture of the *University of Thessaly*. In the same

department, a research team studied the complex (machinery and equipment warehouses) of the American firm *Henry Boot & Sons (Trikala)* and suggested re-use solutions. This company had been carrying out land drying works in the plain of Thessaly from 1932.

The Department of History of the *Ionian University* has been carrying out since 2005 a research project on "Pre-industrial and industrial installations and techniques on the islands of the Ionian, 18th - 20th century". Within the context of the research are being recorded material remains, oral testimony, archival documentation, etc. in connection with each kind of productive installation which has survived in the Ionian Islands.

At the *Institute for Modern Greek Research* at the *National Research Foundation*, the three-year research program on the industrial heritage of the islands of the Aegean was completed in 2004, financed by the Ministry of Aegean. The historic industrial premises of the Aegean islands have been electronically recorded. A Conservation Workshop of historical industrial equipment, in the **Ermoupoli** Industrial Museum was co-ordinated and financed by the same program. A part of the data of the record of the industrial heritage of the Aegean has been incorporated into the digitalisation programme being compiled by the Institute for Modern Greek Research at the National Research Foundation and will soon be available on the Internet.

At the same institute is also being completed a research program on the preservation and highlighting of the industrial heritage, within the framework of which, and with the collaboration of the *University of the Aegean*, five doctoral theses are being compiled on subjects relating to the industrial heritage and ways of utilising this in industrial museums.

A cultural authority of the private sector, the *Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Bank Group*, has been making important efforts of research in the field of industrial archaeology. At this Foundation, a research program on the recording of traditional workshops on **Mt. Pelion** is continuing for the sixth year. A series of research programs which frame the work on museums of the Foundation (see below), such as the program on the history of brick and tile-making, the history of olive oil and its technology has also been completed. There have also been studies on the development of cotton cultivation and the processing of cotton in the **Livadeia (Viotia)** region since the nineteenth century, within the context of a plan for a museum of pre-industrial technology in scheduled watermill buildings, which, however, has not gone forward. A small but interesting program entitled "The art of the tinsmith in the 20th century" has covered an unknown aspect of the history of metalworking in Greece.

One of the ambitions of the *Greek Section of TICCIH* is to make good use of the existing availability of the authorities concerned with the industrial heritage in Greece - together with new ones not yet apparent; it recently embarked upon the creation of a "Register of the Greek Industrial Heritage", with the *NTUA* as the principal co-ordinator, and in collaboration with other universities, the *National Research Foundation*, the *Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Bank Group*, the *Volos Municipal History Centre*, etc. An important step in the direction of the raise of public awareness has been the beginning of educational programs on the industrial heritage in elementary and secondary schools within the context of the environmental education of students. A network of schools has been created and the **Naousa** Centre for Environmental Education has been put in charge of it.

Museums

In the field of technical museums, the increasing activity of the previous decade encouraged expectations of a public policy which, unfortunately, did not materialise. The creation of industrial or pre-industrial museums in Greece has apparently not been one of the priorities of the Ministry of Culture. The only exceptions are the *Water Museum* which was set up in the old water pump-station in **Thessaloniki**, and the *Electric Railways Museum* in **Piraeus**, which was created thanks to the initiative of the Association of Retired Railwaymen. In Thessaloniki another organization called "Friends of Railways" Association has been set up and is running a small railways museum.

In this category of **public museums** the most important projects have been promoted by two academic institutions, the **NTUA** and the *National Research Foundation*. At the Museum of Technology of the French Mining Company at Lavrio, the restoration of the building by the NTUA has been completed (1996 - 2000), but its establishment by the Ministry of Culture, which is responsible for the site, has been pending for ten years now. The **Ermoupoli/Syros** Industrial Museum was opened in 2000. It was constructed by the Municipality of Ermoupoli under the academic supervision of the National Research Foundation, but is still facing serious operating problems because of lack of funding and a reliable framework of operation.

On the other hand, the phenomenon of the setting up of **private or semi-private museums** by private agencies has made its appearance, such as the *Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Bank Group*, the *Silver & Baryte SAM Mining Company* and the *Klifa Soft Drinks Company*.

In this category, the network of industrial and pre-industrial museums being created by the *Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Bank Group*, with the collaboration, in many instances, of local government organisations, has been a great success. The oldest is the Silk Museum at **Soufli in Thraki**, followed by the open-air Waterpower Museum at **Dimitsana in Peloponnese**, the Museum of Olive and Oil at **Sparta**, the **Lesvos** Museum of Industrial Olive Processing.

Within 2007 the Museum of Brick and Tile Manufacture at **Volos** has been completed and the Museum of Marble-Working on **Tinos** Island, is expected to open at the end of the year. Also the Museum of Traditional Occupations and the Environment at **Stymphalia in Peloponnese** by the Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Group is going ahead.

On **Milos** Island, the *Silver & Baryte SA Company* has set up the Mining Museum and a Conference Centre in the old perlite factory. The same company has also created the "Vagoneto" mining park on the premises of the bauxite mines at **Giona**.

At **Trikala** the owners of the *Klifa Soft Drinks Company* have converted the factory (ice factory - refrigerator - soft drinks) into a History and Culture Centre.

At last there should be mentioned the construction of the new *Technical Museum of Thessaloniki*. This exceptional museum of sciences and technology was rehoused in 2004, moving from the old building in which it had operated since 1978 into a modern building of high-quality standards, as *The Centre for the Preservation of Sciences and the Museum of Technology*. The project, financed by the European Union, has been a great success of a team of specialists who have succeeded in creating one of the best museums in the country.

Conferences and events

On the initiative of the Greek Section of *TICCIH*, the 3rd Academic Meeting, on the subject of "Industrial Archives" was held at **Ermoupoli on Syros** island. The minutes of the meeting were published in 2003. In 2003, the Academic Meeting on "Historic Mines in the Aegean, 19th - 20th century" was held on **Milos** island by the *NTUA*, the *Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Bank Group* and other agencies. The minutes were published in 2005.

In 2005 and 2006, the *Greek Section of TICCIH* organised two three-month cycles of events in Athens. The first was entitled "Industrial Heritage Days" and hosted the reading of papers on the protection, preservation and re-use of industrial buildings and equipment. The second was entitled "Industry Memories" and its purpose was a meeting and conversation between its members and executives - mainly engineers - of important old industrial units.

The *Nizhny Tagyl Charter* on the industrial heritage has been translated into Greek and was presented on a special occasion organised by the Greek Section of the *TICCIH*.

In 2005, the *Cultural Foundation of the Piraeus Bank Group*, continuing a long tradition of academic meetings, held its 10th Three-Day Working Session on the history of Greek milk and dairy products. In the same year, it held a day conference on the "History of Paper".

Preservation of Archives

In many cities, on the initiative of the local authorities or academic institutions, the preservation of important archives of industrial enterprises has been achieved. Typical examples are the Archives of the Directorate for

Industry of the Prefecture of **Thessaloniki**, a part of which has been transferred to the *Historical Archive of Macedonia*, the Archive of the **Seriphos** Mines, which has been preserved on the initiative of *TICCIH* and the *NTUA* and is to be transferred to the Historical Archive of **Ermoupoli/Syros**, and the Archive of the *Drapetsona/Piraeus Fertiliser Factory*, which was transferred just before the demolition of the complex and is kept in the Municipality of **Drapetsona**.